

1 Type of the Paper (Article, Review, Communication, etc.)

2 First-principles LCAO calculations of K_2SiF_6 crystal: structural, 3 electronic, elastic, vibrational and dielectric properties

4
5 Leonid L. Rusevich^{1*}, Mikhail G. Brik^{1,2,3,4,5}, Denis Gryaznov^{1*}, Alok M. Srivastava⁶,
6 Ilya Chervyakov¹, Guntars Zvejnieks¹, Dmitry Bocharov^{1,7}, Eugene A. Kotomin¹

- 7 ¹ Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia, 8 Kengaraga Str., LV-1063 Riga, Latvia; levgenijs.Kotomins@cfi.lu.lv (E.A.K.); Ilya.Cervjakovs@cfi.lu.lv (I.Ch.); Guntars.Zvejnieks@cfi.lu.lv (G.Z.); Dmitrijs.Bocharovs@cfi.lu.lv (D.B.)
- 8
9 ² School of Optoelectronic Engineering & CQUPT-BUL Innovation Institute, Chongqing University of Posts and Telecommunications, Chongqing 400065, China
- 10
11 ³ Centre of Excellence for Photoconversion, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia; brik@vin.bg.ac.rs
- 12
13 ⁴ Institute of Physics, University of Tartu, W. Ostwald Str. 1, Tartu 50411, Estonia; mikhail.brik@ut.ee
- 14
15 ⁵ Academy of Romanian Scientists, 3 Ilfov, 050044, Bucharest, Romania
- 16
17 ⁶ Current Lighting Solutions LLC, 1099 Ivanhoe Road, Cleveland, OH 44110, USA; srivastaam@outlook.com
- 18
19 ⁷ Transport and Telecommunication Institute, Lauvas Str. 2, LV-1003 Riga, Latvia; Bocarovs.D@tsi.lv
- * Correspondence: Leonid.Rusevich@cfi.lu.lv (L.L.R.); Denis.Gryaznov@cfi.lu.lv (D.G.)

20 **Abstract:** The results of first-principles calculations of the structural, electronic, elastic, vibrational,
21 dielectric and optical properties, as well as Raman and infrared (IR) spectra, of potassium hexa-
22 afluorosilicate (K_2SiF_6 ; KSF) crystal are discussed. KSF doped with manganese atoms ($KSF:Mn^{4+}$) is
23 known for its ability to function as a phosphor in white LED applications due to the efficient red
24 emission from Mn^{4+} activator ions. The simulations were performed using the CRYSTAL23 com-
25 puter code within the linear combination of atomic orbitals (LCAO) approximation of the density
26 functional theory (DFT). For KSF study, we have applied and compared several DFT functionals
27 (with the emphasis on the hybrid functionals) in combination with Gaussian-type basis sets. In order
28 to determine such optimal combination for computation, two types of basis sets and four different
29 functionals (three advanced hybrid B3LYP, B1WC, PBE0 and one LDA functionals) were used, and
30 the obtained results compared with available experimental data. For the selected basis set and func-
31 tional, the above-mentioned properties of KSF were calculated. In particular, the B1WC functional
32 provides us with the band gap of 9.73 eV. The dependencies of structural, electronic and elastic
33 parameters, as well as the Debye temperature on external pressure (0–20 GPa) were also evaluated
34 and compared with previous calculations. Comprehensive analysis of vibrational properties was
35 performed for the first time; influence of isotopic substitution on the vibrational frequencies was
36 analyzed. IR and Raman spectra were simulated, at that the calculated Raman spectrum is in excel-
37 lent agreement with experimental one.

38 **Keywords:** first-principles calculations; DFT; hybrid functionals; atomic and electronic structure;
39 vibrational, dielectric and elastic properties; Raman and IR spectra; K_2SiF_6 .

40
41 **Citation:** To be added by editorial staff during production.

42 Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

43 Received: date

44 Revised: date

45 Accepted: date

46 Published: date

47 **Copyright:** © 2024 by the authors,
48 Submitted for possible open access
49 publication under the terms and
50 conditions of the Creative Commons
51 Attribution (CC BY) license
52 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

41 1. Introduction

42 In modern lighting applications, solid state white light-emitting diodes (LED) are
43 widely used. Among other materials, the A_2XF_6 ($A=Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs; X=Si, Ge, Sn, Ti$)
44 fluorite phosphors doped with Mn^{4+} are considered nowadays as efficient candidates [1–
45 3]. In particular, $K_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$ is commonly known as a representative material, which has
46 been successfully commercialized [4–13]. This phosphor shows high quantum efficiency

47 and the narrow red emission bands at 613, 631, 636 and 648 nm are suitable for the human
48 eye [14]. Several theoretical studies were published recently [15–17] on the atomic and
49 electronic structure of this phosphor. The first-principles DFT plane wave calculations
50 were focused on the basic K_2SiF_6 (KSF) properties using the GGA (PBE) and LDA func-
51 tionals [15]. This study provided the first estimates of band gap, elastic constants and De-
52 bye temperature, and examined how structural parameters and band gap change under
53 external hydrostatic pressure. A number of different functionals, namely, LDA [15,16],
54 PBE [15–17], GGA [18], SCAN, HSE06, PBE0, PBE+U [16] were compared using the plane
55 wave basis set with the emphasis on the band gap value. Indeed, a significant problem
56 still remains the lack of experimental data on the KSF band gap. We can only note the
57 paper [19] where the fundamental absorption edge of pure KSF was determined to occur
58 at ~ 5.6 eV, which is probably a very underestimated value for the band gap. Based on the
59 experiments for other fluorides [20], KSF band gap is expected to be about 10 eV.

60 In this paper, we have performed for the first time detailed first-principles calcula-
61 tions of a wide range of KFS properties using the state-of-the-art quantum chemical ap-
62 proach — linear combination of the atomic orbitals (LCAO) combined with the hybrid
63 functional, as implemented in the CRYSTAL code [21] widely used for insulating materi-
64 als modelling [22,23]. Taking into account the practical importance of $KSF:Mn^{4+}$ as phos-
65 phor, the hybrid functionals are of significant importance to apply here to defectless ma-
66 terial first within the formalism of LCAO. It is worth mentioning that the hybrid function-
67 als and Gaussian-type basis sets have been successfully applied to fluorides earlier [24,25]
68 and other wide band gap materials (like diamond, Al_2O_3 , $MgAl_2O_4$). Thus, the present
69 study continues our recent DFT consideration of KSF [15] (based on the plane wave basis
70 set and LDA and GGA functionals) by using several DFT functionals, including hybrid
71 and conventional LDA functionals, and Gaussian-type basis sets. In this way, we also fill
72 the gap in the application of DFT methods to KSF research. The results for two Gaussian-
73 type basis sets and several DFT functionals for the atomic, electronic and elastic properties
74 are compared with each other, and previous plane wave calculations. In addition, calcula-
75 tions of the vibrational frequencies were performed for the first time for this host, to the
76 best of the authors' knowledge. The comprehensive data obtained in this study are very
77 important for collecting detailed information about prospective phosphor materials, cre-
78 ating a comparative database of crystalline solids used as phosphors, and assessment of
79 the perspectives for using crystalline solids in lighting applications.

81 2. Materials and Methods

82 2.1. The equilibrium structure of KSF

83 The perfect KSF has a face-centered cubic crystal structure with $Fm-3m$ space group
84 symmetry (space group Nr. 225; SG 225) and experimental lattice constant $a = 8.134$ Å [15].
85 The crystallographic (conventional) cubic unit cell of this crystal lattice contains 36 atoms
86 and the Wyckoff positions of atoms are K:8c(1/4, 1/4, 1/4), Si:4a(0, 0, 0), F:24e(x , 0, 0) (after
87 full geometry optimization we obtained $x=0.20998$; see Table 3). In this structure, K ions
88 are 12-fold coordinated by the fluorine ions, but Si ions are surrounded by 6 fluorine ions,

89 which form a perfect octahedron. Experimental values of K–F and Si–F distances are 2.897
90 Å and 1.683 Å, respectively [15,26]. A simulated perfect KSF crystal structure with the
91 highlighted crystallographic cubic unit cell is presented in Figure 1. Note that the SiF₆
92 octahedra are located at the vertices of the cube and at the centers of its faces.
93
94

95
96 **Figure 1.** Calculated crystal structure and crystallographic unit cell (36 atoms) of KSF. K
97 atoms — violet balls, Si — blue, F — grey. SiF₆ octahedra are highlighted. The cube drawn
98 with black lines represents a unit cell.
99

100 2.2. Computational details

101 The first-principles (*ab initio*) simulations of KSF were performed within the LCAO
102 approximation, as implemented in CRYSTAL23 computer code [21]. By default, calcula-
103 tions in the CRYSTAL program are performed for a primitive unit cell, which in the case
104 of KSF consists of only 9 atoms. This study provides a detailed analysis of the structural,
105 electronic, elastic, vibrational, dielectric, and optical properties of KSF, including simula-
106 tion of one-phonon Raman and infrared (IR) spectra.

107 At the beginning, to define an optimal combination of basis set and functional for the
108 calculations, the perfect KSF was simulated using two different basis sets of Gaussian type
109 functions and four functionals. After that, the obtained results were compared with avail-
110 able experimental data. “Basis set 1” included the following three all-electron basis sets.
111 The basis set for K contains (8s)-(6sp)-(5sp)-(1sp)-(1sp)-(3d) contractions [27] and it is
112 available (like all other used basis sets) on the CRYSTAL Basis Sets Library web site [28]
113 as K_86-511G_dovesi_1991 basis set; Si basis set [29] with (8s)-(6sp)-(3sp)-(1sp)-(1sp)-(1d)
114 contractions (Si_86-311G**_pascal_2005); (7s)-(3sp)-(1sp)-(1sp) F basis set [30] (F_7-
115 311G_nada_1993). Second basis set (“TZVP_2012 basis set”) included three following all-
116 electron basis sets [31]: (8s)-(4s)-(2s)-(1s)-(1s)-(1s)-(6p)-(3p)-(1p)-(1p)-(1d) K basis set
117 (K_pob_TZVP_2012), (7s)-(3s)-(2s)-(1s)-(1s)-(5p)-(1p)-(1p)-(1p)-(1d) Si basis set

(Si_pob_TZVP_2012) and (6s)-(2s)-(1s)-(1s)-(4p)-(1p)-(1p)-(1d) basis set for F (F_pob_TZVP_2012). In preliminary calculations, three global hybrid DFT-HF exchange-correlation functionals (B1WC, PBE0, B3LYP) and one LDA functional were used. The single-parameter B1WC functional [21,32] suggests 16% (by default) of the exact Hartree-Fock (HF) exchange due to improved Wu-Cohen GGA exchange part [33] in a combination with the Perdew-Wang PW-GGA correlation functional [21,34]. The PBE0 functional combines PBE exchange functional with 25% (by default) of HF exchange and the PBE correlation functional [21,35]. Three-parameter B3LYP functional [21,36] combines BECKE GGA exchange contribution [37], the LDA exchange contribution, the LYP (Lee-Yang-Parr) GGA correlation contribution [38] and the LDA correlation contribution with the exact HF exchange (denoted as A parameter in [21]) in the amount of 20% (by default). Besides, the exchange and correlation parameters are given by $B=0.9$ and $C=0.81$ (as is suggested by default in [21], keyword NONLOCAL). The chosen B parameter corresponds to the exchange parameter $a_x=(1-A)B=0.72$ suggested in Becke's original paper [36]. Finally, the LDA functional was presented, probably, by the most popular LDA formulation — LDA exchange functional and VWN (Vosko-Wilk-Nusair) correlation functional (also known as VWN5) [21]. This LDA formulation is also known as S-VWN.

The five threshold parameters controlling the accuracy of the calculation of the bi-electronic Coulomb and HF exchange series (truncation criteria) [21] have been set to 9, 9, 9, 9, 18. A regular Monkhorst-Pack mesh of points in the reciprocal space with shrinking factor 8 has been used for calculations. The integrations were performed on a default predefined "extra extra large" pruned grid (XXLGRID) consisting of 99 radial points and a maximum of 1454 angular points in the regions relevant for chemical bonding. The Self-Consistent Field (SCF) convergence threshold parameter for the total energy was set to 10^{-10} Hartree (Ha) in all calculations. In order to achieve a very accurate convergence of geometry required for vibrational frequencies calculation, during a full geometry optimization the following convergence criteria were used: RMS (root mean square) of the gradient (TOLDEG) is 0.00003 Ha/Bohr, RMS of the displacement (TOLDEX) is 0.00012 Bohr.

After comparison of obtained results with experimental data, we have concluded that the best combination of basis set and functional is the "TZVP_2012 basis set" and B1WC functional (see next section). Previous studies have shown that B1WC functional yields reliable results in calculations of different properties of Ti-perovskite crystals, their solid solutions and heterostructures, in particular, band gaps of these systems [39,40].

The dependence of some selected structural, electronic and elastic properties of KSF on the external hydrostatic pressure (0–20 GPa) was evaluated to see how the pressure-induced changes of the interatomic distances can tune the host's parameters. The CRYSTAL program implements a procedure that allows to calculate the elastic properties of crystalline materials, also under pressure [21,41,42]. A complete vibrational analysis was performed for KSF. For the equilibrium geometry, the transverse optical (TO) vibrational frequencies and vibrational contribution to the dielectric tensor were calculated at the Γ -point (in the center of the first Brillouin zone) within the harmonic approximation. In these calculations, the step size of displacement along each Cartesian axis for numerical derivatives (STEPSIZE) was modified to 0.01 Å (0.003 Å by default). The complex dielectric function $\varepsilon(\nu)$, depending on the frequency ν and associated with the vibrational modes, is the sum of the electronic (high-frequency) and ionic (vibrational) components. It is calculated in CRYSTAL code on the basis of a classical dispersion relation of Drude-Lorentz model [21,43] and is defined as

$$\varepsilon(\nu) = \varepsilon_{el} + \sum_j \frac{f_j \nu_j^2}{\nu_j^2 - \nu^2 - i\nu\gamma_j} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where ε_{el} is the high-frequency dielectric constant, ν_j , f_j and γ_j are the frequency of the j^{th} TO IR-active vibrational mode, the oscillator strength and the damping factor, respectively [21].

The static dielectric tensor (constant, in our case) $\varepsilon(0)$ also includes both the electronic and the ionic contributions to the dielectric response. From Equation (1), it is equal to

$$\varepsilon(0) = \varepsilon_{el} + \sum_j f_j = \varepsilon_{el} + F \quad , \quad (2)$$

where the vibrational contribution F is the sum of the oscillator strengths. Wherein, the oscillator strengths for an isotropic crystal are computed by means of the expression

$$f_j = \frac{4\pi Z_j^2}{V \nu_j^2} \quad , \quad (3)$$

where V is the cell volume and Z_j^2 is the mass-weighted effective mode Born charge [44].

The electronic contribution ε_{el} has been calculated in CRYSTAL through the coupled perturbed Hartree-Fock/Kohn-Sham (CPHF/CPKS) scheme, adapted for periodic systems [45,46].

The real and imaginary parts of the refractive index $n(\nu)$ are obtained from the complex dielectric function $\varepsilon(\nu)$ [21]. The integrated intensity I_n of the IR-active vibrational mode ν_n is computed assuming the isotropic response. A few different techniques may be used in the CRYSTAL code for the IR intensities calculation. We have computed IR intensities through both Berry phase approach, which implies numerical differentiations, and CPHF approach, which is entirely analytical [21,47]. Both methods give close results, as it was observed before in the study of SrTiO₃, BaTiO₃ [48] and diamond [49,50] crystals. In turn, the Raman scattering intensities of the Raman-active modes are calculated by a fully analytical method, which is based on the self-consistent solution of first- and second-order CPHF/CPKS equations for the electronic response to external electric fields at the equilibrium geometry [51,52]. Additionally, one-phonon Raman and IR absorbance spectra were simulated using corresponding TO vibrational modes. Both types of spectra were calculated as a convolution of intensities of these modes with the Lorentzian resolution function (FWHM = 8 cm⁻¹).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Choice of the optimal combination of basis sets and functional

To achieve the most accurate description of KSF vibrational and dielectric properties it was crucial to carefully select the optimal combination of basis sets and functional based on experimental values of the main structural, electronic and optical parameters. Tables 1 and 2 present various structural and electronic parameters calculated using two types of basis sets ("Basis set 1" and "TZVP_2012 basis set") and four different functionals (B1WC, B3LYP, PBE0, LDA), along with the corresponding available experimental data ("Expt."). Data in the tables include: lattice constant a , distances between ions (Si-F, K-F), direct band gap E_g , calculated Mulliken (effective atomic) charges of ions and refractive index n , determined as the square root of the real part of the electronic (high-frequency) dielectric constant. Values in parenthesis show the difference between calculated and experimental data (relative error in %).

Table 1. Lattice constant a , interionic distances (Si–F, K–F), band gap E_g , Mulliken (effective atomic) charges of ions and refractive index n of KSF, calculated with using “Basis set 1” and four functionals (B1WC, B3LYP, PBE0, LDA) at zero external pressure in comparison with corresponding experimental data (“Expt.”).

	B1WC	B3LYP	PBE0	LDA	Expt. [15]
a , Å	8.134 (0.00%)	8.263 (1.59%)	8.197 (0.77%)	7.818 (-3.88%)	8.134
Si–F, Å	1.704 (1.25%)	1.715 (1.90%)	1.706 (1.37%)	1.701 (1.07%)	1.683
K–F, Å	2.895 (-0.07%)	2.942 (1.55%)	2.918 (0.72%)	2.776 (-4.18%)	2.897
E_g , eV	9.83	10.03	10.84	7.88	
F, e	-0.410	-0.455	-0.430	-0.370	
Si, e	0.534	0.807	0.649	0.320	
K, e	0.964	0.961	0.966	0.950	
n	1.264 (-5.67%)	1.249 (-6.79%)	1.249 (-6.79%)	1.326 (-1.04%)	1.34

Table 2. Lattice constant a , interionic distances (Si–F, K–F), band gap E_g , Mulliken (effective atomic) charges of ions and refractive index n of KSF, calculated with using “TZVP_2012 basis set” and four functionals (B1WC, B3LYP, PBE0, LDA) at zero external pressure in comparison with corresponding experimental data (“Expt.”).

	B1WC	B3LYP	PBE0	LDA	Expt. [15]
a , Å	8.086 (-0.59%)	8.200 (0.81%)	8.153 (0.23%)	7.796 (-4.16%)	8.134
Si–F, Å	1.698 (0.89%)	1.709 (1.54%)	1.700 (1.01%)	1.696 (0.77%)	1.683
K–F, Å	2.877 (-0.69%)	2.919 (0.76%)	2.903 (0.21%)	2.768 (-4.45%)	2.897
E_g , eV	9.73	9.96	10.69	7.90	
F, e	-0.585	-0.605	-0.604	-0.539	
Si, e	1.807	1.919	1.899	1.679	
K, e	0.852	0.856	0.861	0.778	
n	1.321 (-1.42%)	1.305 (-2.61%)	1.305 (-2.61%)	1.381 (3.06%)	1.34

As can be seen from the tables, the structural parameters (lattice constant and distances between ions) are described quite well by all combinations of hybrid functionals and basis sets. Here the errors do not exceed 2%. Wherein, the LDA functional describes the structural parameters much worse which is in agreement with the plane wave calculations [15,16]. Note, that absolutely all present simulations slightly overestimate the Si–F distance (a positive sign of the error value in the parenthesis). Interestingly, the absolute value and sign of error for a and the K–F distance are correlated.

All present calculations give a direct band gap, and all hybrid functionals give close (within 1 eV) band gap around 10 eV. In contrast, the LDA functional gives a significantly lower band gap (this is consistent with the results of plane wave calculations [15,16]), as expected. However, our calculated value of the band gap ~ 7.9 eV obtained by the LDA functional is even larger than the GGA results of ~ 7.0 and 7.2 eV in Ref. [17] and Ref. [18], respectively. Interestingly, the same trend in the band gap for the comparison between the LDA and GGA functionals was already seen in previous plane wave calculations in [15,16]. The present band gap calculated with the B1WC (PBE0) functional (Table 2) is very close to that found with the HSE06 (PBE0) functional and plane wave calculations [16], i.e. 9.73 (10.69) vs 9.68 (10.44) eV. Due to the lack of reliable experimental data, the calculated band gap value cannot be directly compared with the experiment, but the computations reveal that KSF can definitely be classified as a wide band gap compound. Regarding ion charges, the Si ion charge, calculated using “Basis set 1”, appears to be too small. Moreover, the LDA functional differs from the results of the hybrid functionals for the charges by the fact that the charges of cations are significantly smaller pointing at underestimated

243 ionicity of the material. Refractive index n is underestimated in all computations with
 244 “Basis set 1”, but when using “TZVP_2012 basis set” the B1WC functional shows the best
 245 agreement with the experimental data.

246 As a result, we conclude that the role of the hybrid functional is crucial for the elec-
 247 tronic properties of the material (the band gap value and charges). After analyzing the
 248 data in Table 1 and Table 2, we have chosen the B1WC functional and the “TZVP_2012
 249 basis set” as the optimal combination for calculations. All further computations were per-
 250 formed using this combination.

3.2. Electronic density of states (DOS)

253 **Figure 2.** Projected and total electronic DOSs of KSF calculated with the hybrid B1WC
 254 functional and “TZVP_2012 basis set” at zero external pressure. Contributions of two K,
 255 one Si and six F atoms are shown. The zero energy value corresponds to the Fermi level.
 256 (a) Top of valence band (negative values of abscissa axis); (b) Bottom of conducting band
 257 (band gap is 9.73 eV).

258 The calculated electronic density of states (DOS) of KSF, shown in Figure 2, reveals
 259 that F ions make an absolutely dominant contribution to the electronic DOS of the valence
 260 band (VB), while the conducting band (CB) consists mainly of cation states. Interestingly,
 261 that at least the top of the VB consists of several more or less narrow (~0.5 eV) sub-bands.
 262 The presence of such five sub-bands in the energy range between 0 and -4 eV (Figure 2a)
 263 is consistent with the GGA functional and plane wave calculations in Refs. [17,18]. In par-
 264 ticular, the two sub-bands lying in deep energies ranges between -2.5 and -4 eV are sepa-
 265 rated by almost 0.8 eV gap whereas the other sub-bands have the separation of ~0.5 eV.

266 On the other hand, the nature of Si–F bond in KSF could be even better understood
 267 from the overlap population analysis. It reveals +0.24 |e| (obtained with B1WC) for the
 268 overlap population of Si–F bond, reflecting its quite covalent nature. It is also in line with
 269 such smaller effective atomic charges (Table 2) of fluorine ions in the comparison with
 270 more ionic MgF₂: -0.59 |e| in KSF (B1WC) vs -0.87 |e| in MgF₂ (the result of PBE0 in Ref.
 271 [24]).

3.3. Elastic properties and effect of external pressure

272 **Table 3.** Dependence of KSF lattice constant a , non-dimensional free x coordinate of the F
 273 ion (Wyckoff position 24e in SG $Fm-3m$), interionic distances (Si–F, K–F), band gap E_g and
 274 Mulliken (effective atomic) charges of ions on external pressure. “TZVP_2012 basis set”
 275 and the B1WC functional were used for calculations.

	0 GPa	4 GPa	8 GPa	12 GPa	16 GPa	20 GPa
a , Å	8.086	7.759	7.563	7.424	7.316	7.227
x	0.20998	0.21814	0.22322	0.22685	0.22969	0.23201
Si–F, Å	1.698	1.693	1.688	1.684	1.680	1.677
K–F, Å	2.877	2.755	2.682	2.630	2.591	2.559
E_g , eV	9.73	10.29	10.70	11.01	11.27	11.50
F, e	-0.585	-0.575	-0.569	-0.566	-0.563	-0.561
Si, e	1.807	1.802	1.803	1.807	1.811	1.817
K, e	0.852	0.824	0.807	0.793	0.783	0.774

Table 4. Effect of pressure on the elastic constants (C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{44}), bulk modulus B , Hill shear modulus G , Young modulus E and Poisson ratio ν of KSF. “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

	0 GPa	4 GPa	8 GPa	12 GPa	16 GPa	20 GPa
C_{11} , GPa	36.95	61.82	84.65	107.39	129.47	151.39
C_{12} , GPa	14.94	34.14	52.10	69.63	86.52	102.94
C_{44} , GPa	12.74	20.11	26.95	34.20	41.51	49.12
B , GPa	22.28	43.36	62.95	82.22	100.83	119.09
G , GPa	12.02	17.31	22.01	26.95	31.86	36.98
E , GPa	30.56	45.83	59.14	72.88	86.48	100.54
ν	0.27	0.32	0.34	0.35	0.36	0.36

Table 3 and Table 4 present the dependences of selected structural and electronic parameters, as well as some elastic constants of KSF on external hydrostatic pressure. Data from Table 3 reveal that structural parameters of KSF (lattice constant a and distances between ions) decrease monotonically with increasing pressure. Both K–F and a dependences can be approximated by the second order polynomials, wherein the linear fit provides sufficient precision for description (with more or less the same accuracy) of the pressure effect on the Si–F interionic distance (Figure 3). As expected, the application of external pressure leads to a decrease in the lattice constant and interionic distances. However, it is important to pay attention to the rate of decreasing of these parameters. When the pressure changes from 0 till 20 GPa, the lattice constant a , Si–F and K–F distances decrease by 10.6%, 1.2% and 11.1%, respectively. This result shows the high stiffness of the Si–F bond and that the decrease of unit cell volume with pressure occurs mainly due to a reduction in the size of the KF_{12} polyhedra. Note that as the pressure increases, the relative position of the F ion in the unit cell changes. This is indicated by the variation in the non-dimensional free x coordinate of the F ion in the Wyckoff position 24e of the crystal lattice. This coordinate increases monotonically with pressure (Table 3), what means that a relative Si–F interionic distance will increase, while K–F will decrease.

Figure 3. Dependences of the lattice constant (a) and the interatomic distances Si–F (right vertical axis) and K–F (left vertical axis) (b) on the external pressure with corresponding fitting (dotted lines). Calculations were performed with “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

The band gap monotonically increases with increasing of pressure (see Table 3), what is quite expected for direct band gap. It is a non-linear dependence and it can be described by a second order polynomial (Figure 4). The increase of band gap value is 18.2% at the pressure change from 0 till 20 GPa.

Figure 4. Dependence of the KSF band gap value on the external pressure with corresponding fitting (orange dotted line). “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

Note, that the use of a fitting (Figures 3 and 4) allows to interpolate the corresponding parameters at any pressure value in the studied range.

The Mulliken charges (in absolute value) of the K and F ions decrease monotonically with increasing pressure, whereas the charge of the Si ion remains relatively constant (Table 3). These facts allow concluding that chemical bonds become somewhat more covalent with rise of pressure.

Table 4 demonstrates the pressure influence on the KSF elastic properties. The symmetric elastic tensor of KSF (as a cubic crystal system) has only three independent constants C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{44} . These constants, as well as bulk modulus (B), Hill shear modulus (G), Young modulus (E) and Poisson ratio (ν) are presented in Table 4. It is important to note that the Hill shear modulus is defined as the average of the Voigt (an upper limit for G)

and Reuss (a lower limit for G) shear moduli [15,17], and the Voigt and Reuss bulk moduli of KSF are equal to each other. Our values of the elastic constants C_{11} and C_{12} , as well as the bulk modulus B (Table 4, the hybrid B1WC functional), calculated at zero-pressure, are slightly larger than those calculated in plane wave calculations with GGA functional in Refs. [15,17]. The same situation is with the constants G , E and ν if we compare our results (Table 4) and the results in Ref. [15] (E and ν) and Ref. [17] (shear modulus G). At the same time, the elastic constant C_{44} in our calculations (Table 4) is somewhat smaller compared to the results of GGA calculations in Refs. [15,17]. Under an external pressure of 20 GPa, all elastic constants C_{ij} , as well as the moduli B and G , are larger in calculations with the hybrid B1WC functional (Table 4) than with GGA functional [17]. An inspection of Table 4 clearly shows that all elastic constants increase with increasing of pressure. The authors of Ref. [17], who calculated, in particular, three elastic constants, bulk and shear moduli depending on pressure, made similar conclusions.

3.4. Vibrational properties, IR and Raman spectra

Table 5. Calculated transverse optical (TO) vibrational modes at the Γ -point of the KSF Brillouin zone (BZ). Letters A and I in the third column indicate whether the mode is, respectively, active or inactive for IR and Raman scatterings. “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

Modes	Frequencies, cm ⁻¹	IR–Raman
F _{1g}	72	I–I
F _{2g}	131	I–A
F _{1u}	137	A–I
F _{2u}	264	I–I
F _{2g}	398	I–A
F _{1u}	471	A–I
E _g	492	I–A
A _{1g} *	649	I–A
F _{1u}	754	A–I

* Note, that this mode is denoted as A_g in the CRYSTAL output file.

As a primitive unit cell of KSF consists 9 atoms, there are 27 normal lattice vibrations at the Γ -point of the Brillouin zone (BZ) of this system. Three of them are acoustic vibrations, other 24 — optical vibrations, which are distributed over 9 phonon modes. TO modes with corresponding frequencies, calculated in this study, are presented in Table 5. It is clear from the table that the set of phonon modes is given by $F_{1g} + 2F_{2g} + 3F_{1u} + F_{2u} + E_g + A_{1g}$, i.e., includes seven triply degenerate modes (F-modes), one doubly degenerate mode (E_g) and one non-degenerate mode (A_{1g}). Three F_{1u} modes are IR-active, four modes ($2F_{2g} + E_g + A_{1g}$) — Raman-active, two modes (F_{1g} and F_{2u}) are silent (neither Raman- nor IR-active). Interestingly, the IR- and Raman-active modes are strictly separated (no one mode is both IR- and Raman-active). All calculated TO vibrational modes are located in the range of 70–755 cm⁻¹ (2.1–22.6 THz).

Figure 5. One-phonon IR absorbance spectrum of KSF simulated with the B1WC functional and “TZVP_2012 basis set”.

The relevant simulated one-phonon IR and Raman spectra are presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. The three IR-active modes are well separated by frequency (Table 5), so each peak in the IR spectrum is generated by only one vibrational mode, and there are three distinct peaks in the spectrum (Figure 5). The most intensive peak corresponds to 754 cm^{-1} F_{1u} TO phonon mode. The analysis of atom displacements in this mode reveals that Si atoms demonstrate the maximal displacements; moreover, these atoms take part in vibrations along all axes. At the same time, each fluorine atom participates in vibrations, mainly, along only some one axis, but contribution of K atoms to this mode is negligible. On the contrary, K atoms give the main contribution to the first peak (137 cm^{-1}) of IR spectrum, although the contributions of Si and F atoms are also significant. All atoms vibrate in this mode along all axes. Finally, the middle peak (471 cm^{-1}) arises due to vibrations of F and Si atoms along all axes. K atoms practically do not vibrate in this mode.

To check the conclusions, derived from the analysis of the atom displacements in the vibrational modes, we have used the option of the isotopic substitution (the possibility to modify the atomic masses of specific atoms), implemented in the CRYSTAL code [21]. We have compared the vibrational frequencies computed using standard atomic masses and those obtained with new relative isotopic masses. Such analysis gives the possibility to evaluate the contributions of the selected atoms to the vibrational modes. In general, an increase of atomic masses leads to a decrease of vibrational frequencies, but this decrease depends on a contribution of a corresponding atom (group of atoms) to the particular vibrational mode. We have used this technique previously when investigating the point defects in diamonds [49,50]. In the current study, we have increased relative masses of atoms in KSF approximately by 10%, and the isotopic shifts of vibrational modes frequencies were calculated for three different cases: i) relative atomic mass of Si atom is changed from 28 to 31; ii) masses of all K atoms is changed from 39 to 43; iii) masses of all F atoms — from 19 to 21.

As a result, returning to the IR-active modes, we conclude that isotopic substitution fully confirms the estimates obtained from the atom displacement analysis. The isotopic shift of mode 754 cm^{-1} is -23.2 cm^{-1} in the case of isotopic substitution of Si atom, -13.2 cm^{-1} at the change of F atoms masses and only a few thousandths cm^{-1} (practically negligible) in the case of K atoms. The isotopic shift of mode 471 cm^{-1} is -4.6 cm^{-1} for Si atom isotopic substitution, -19.1 cm^{-1} for F atoms and again a few thousandths cm^{-1} for K atoms. The lowest frequency IR-mode (137 cm^{-1}) has isotopic shift -0.4 cm^{-1} for Si atom substitution, -2.0 cm^{-1} for F atoms and -4.2 cm^{-1} for K atoms. Thus, vibrations of Si and F atoms contribute

to all IR-modes, but K atoms vibrate only in one mode (137 cm^{-1}) and their contribution to other two modes can be neglected.

Figure 6. Raman spectrum of KSF simulated with the B1WC functional and “TZVP_2012 basis set”.

As in the case of the IR spectrum, each peak of the Raman spectrum (Figure 6) is also formed by one vibrational mode only, since the Raman modes are well separated by frequency (Table 5). Interestingly, that both Raman-active and silent modes are associated with vibrations of some one type of atoms (either K or F). Let us first consider the Raman-active modes. Relative intensities of Raman lines (they are normalized to the most intensive line) corresponding to Raman-active modes are 0.034:0.183:0.062:1 (for the lines with frequencies 131 , 398 , 492 and 649 cm^{-1} , respectively). These four modes generate four peaks in the Raman spectrum (Figure 6). One peak is dominant (649 cm^{-1}).

It is noteworthy that Si atoms remain stationary in all Raman-active modes. Vibrations of K atoms along all axes produce the 131 cm^{-1} mode. The isotopic shift of this mode for K atoms isotopic substitution is -6.3 cm^{-1} . Wherein, the isotopic shift for F atoms is less than one thousandth cm^{-1} . On the contrary, the 398 cm^{-1} mode arises from vibrations of F atoms and the isotopic shift due to K atoms is less than one thousandth cm^{-1} . The vibrations of each F atoms in this mode occurs in some one plane and the isotopic shift due to F atoms is -19.4 cm^{-1} . Exclusively vibrations of F atoms form the 492 and 649 cm^{-1} modes (Si and K atoms do not vibrate at all in these modes). At the same time, each F atom vibrates only along some one axis.

We would like to emphasize that our simulated Raman spectrum is in excellent agreement with the experimental spectrum measured for KSF:Mn^{4+} at ambient pressure [53]. The experimental spectrum consists of four characteristic lines at ~ 120 , ~ 405 , ~ 475 and $\sim 655\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a dominant peak at $\sim 655\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These frequency values are very close to the frequencies of the calculated modes that form the simulated Raman spectrum (see Table 5 and Figure 6). Moreover, the authors in Ref. [53] concluded that the three highest frequency lines in the experimental spectrum (405 , 475 and 655 cm^{-1}) are associated with vibrations of SiF_6 octahedra. This completely coincides with the results of our vibrational analysis and the statement that the vibrations of F atoms entirely (for lines 492 and 649 cm^{-1}) or almost entirely (for line 398 cm^{-1}) form the corresponding peaks in the simulated Raman spectrum (see paragraph above).

The silent modes are also formed by vibrations of F atoms. In these modes, each F atom vibrates in some one plane. Si and K atoms remains stationary in silent modes. The

isotopic shifts for F atoms isotopic substitution are -3.5 cm^{-1} (mode 72 cm^{-1}) and -12.9 cm^{-1} (mode 264 cm^{-1}).

3.5. Dielectric and optical properties

The static dielectric tensor $\epsilon(0)$, given by Equation (2), is a constant in the case of defectless KSF, since the 3 diagonal elements of the second rank tensor are equal and the off-diagonal elements are zero. The estimation of $\epsilon(0)$ was performed in two steps. Firstly, the high-frequency contribution ϵ_{el} was calculated, containing only the electronic response. After that, the vibrational contribution ϵ_{vib} to the static dielectric tensor was computed during the calculation of TO vibrational frequencies. Herewith, ϵ_{vib} is the sum of the vibrational contributions of each IR-active mode. Our calculations give for the electronic component, also called optical dielectric constant, the value $\epsilon_{el}=1.745$. Typically, ϵ_{el} is not the main source of a possible high $\epsilon(0)$. The large static dielectric constant usually arises from the lattice (vibrational) contribution. Our computations reveal that the sum of the vibrational contributions of three IR-active modes to the static dielectric constant is $\epsilon_{vib}=2.628$, which is quite comparable to the electronic contribution ϵ_{el} . Wherein, the main contribution to the ϵ_{vib} (2.160 from 2.628) comes from the vibrational mode at 137 cm^{-1} . This mode is the lowest frequency vibrational mode among the modes contributing to the static dielectric constant. This result is consistent with Equation (3), where oscillator strength is inversely proportional to the square of the frequency. Thus, for perfect KSF our calculations yield a static dielectric constant of $\epsilon(0)=4.373$.

Figure 7. Real $\text{Re}[\epsilon(\nu)]$ and imaginary $\text{Im}[\epsilon(\nu)]$ parts of KSF relative permittivity. “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

In general, a permittivity is a complex function with an imaginary part, associated with the conductivity, which determines the absorption. The CRYSTAL code allows to calculate the real and imaginary parts of the complex dielectric function $\epsilon(\nu)$ depending on the vibrational frequency ν . Wherein, the maxima of the imaginary part of the dielectric function correspond to the frequencies of the TO vibrational modes. Figure 7 exhibits the real and imaginary parts of the calculated dielectric function of KSF. Three absorption bands are observed, corresponding to three IR-active vibrational modes of the material. In these regions $\text{Im}[\epsilon(\nu)]$ has maxima, and $\text{Re}[\epsilon(\nu)]$ drops sharply. Note, that the real part of the dielectric function at $\nu=0$, $\text{Re}[\epsilon(0)]$, is the static dielectric constant $\epsilon(0)$, and the presence of negative values of $\text{Re}[\epsilon(\nu)]$ indicates that electromagnetic waves of the corresponding frequencies will not propagate in the medium, but will be reflected from its boundary.

485
486

487

488

489

490

491

492

493

494

495

496

497

498

499

500

501

502

503

504

505

506

507

508

Figure 8. Real $\text{Re}[n(\nu)]$ and imaginary $\text{Im}[n(\nu)]$ parts of KSF refractive index. “TZVP_2012 basis set” and the B1WC functional.

509

510

511

512

The refractive index, calculated from the high-frequency (electronic) contribution ϵ_{el} to the static dielectric constant, is 1.321, which is in a very good agreement with the experimental data (see Table 2). A complex frequency-dependent refractive index $n(\nu)$ is used to describe the propagation of electromagnetic waves in absorbing materials. In this context, the imaginary part is responsible for attenuation, and the real part is responsible for refraction. The real and imaginary parts of such complex refractive index of KSF are presented in Figure 8. Similar to the dielectric function, the imaginary part $\text{Im}[n(\nu)]$ has three maxima corresponding to IR-active modes of KSF. Far from these areas, in frequency ranges where the imaginary part is close to zero and the medium is transparent for electromagnetic waves, the real part of the refractive index $\text{Re}[n(\nu)]$ increases slightly with frequency (normal dispersion). However, it decreases rapidly in the region of absorption bands (anomalous dispersion). Note, that $\text{Re}[n(0)]$ is equal to the square root of the static dielectric constant $\epsilon(0)$, and possible values of the real part of the refractive index below unity indicate that the phase speed of light of certain frequencies in this medium can exceed the speed of light in vacuum.

3.6. Debye temperature evaluation

In the last subsection, we estimate the elastic wave velocities in a crystal and Debye temperature from the obtained elastic constants. The longitudinal v_l and transverse v_t velocities of elastic waves can be calculated [15,17,54] as

$$v_l = \sqrt{\frac{3B + 4G}{3\rho}}, \quad v_t = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}}, \quad (4)$$

513

514

515

516

where B is the bulk modulus, G is the shear modulus and ρ is the material density. Using v_l and v_t from (4), it is possible to calculate the average elastic wave velocity (an effective sonic velocity) v_m , weighted by the number of polarization states [15,17,55]:

$$v_m = \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{2}{v_t^3} + \frac{1}{v_l^3} \right) \right]^{-1/3}. \quad (5)$$

517

Finally, using v_m from (5), Debye temperature Θ_D is calculated by the formula [15,17,56]

518

$$\Theta_D = \frac{h}{k} \left(\frac{3nN_A \rho}{4\pi \mu} \right)^{1/3} v_m, \quad (6)$$

519

520

521

522

523

524

525

526

where h and k are the Planck's and Boltzmann's constants, respectively, N_A is the Avogadro's number, μ is the molecular weight, n denotes the number of atoms per formula unit (9 for KSF).

Table 6. Dependences of KSF density ρ , the elastic wave velocities (v_l , v_t , v_m) in crystal and Debye temperature Θ_D on pressure. The data in this table were obtained using results of first-principles calculations with "TZVP_2012 basis set" and the B1WC functional.

	0 GPa	4 GPa	8 GPa	12 GPa	16 GPa	20 GPa
ρ , kg/m ³	2763	3126	3377	3570	3730	3869
v_l , m/s	3723	4610	5228	5753	6198	6597
v_t , m/s	2086	2353	2553	2748	2923	3092
v_m , m/s	2321	2637	2868	3090	3289	3480
Θ_D , K	282	334	373	409	442	473

527

528

529

530

531

532

533

534

535

536

537

538

539

540

Thus, using the values of B and G moduli from Table 4 and Equations (4)–(6), elastic wave velocities and Debye temperature can be calculated as functions of pressure. It is important to take into account in computations the dependence of density on pressure, since density increases by 40% when pressure changes from 0 to 20 GPa. The results of these calculations are summarized in Table 6. The obtained data demonstrate that velocities and Debye temperature, like the density of crystal, increase with increasing pressure. Comparing our results with previous calculations [17], we can conclude that both the velocities and (especially) the Debye temperatures coincide quite well at 0 GPa. However, the rate of growth of all these parameters in our calculations is slightly higher. Unfortunately, due to the lack of experimental data, the results of calculations cannot be compared with experiment even at atmospheric pressure.

541

4. Conclusions

542

543

544

545

546

547

548

549

550

551

552

553

554

555

556

557

558

The first-principles calculations of a wide range of the structural and physical properties for the perfect KSF crystal were performed in the present paper. When doped with Mn⁴⁺ ions, KSF is widely used as a commercial red phosphor in white LEDs. Several computational settings were used to determine the one whose results best agreed with the experimental data. We applied the hybrid DFT functionals and Gaussian-type basis sets for KSF study. Specifically, we found differences in the lattice parameters, interionic distances and electronic band gaps between conventional methods like LDA, GGA and hybrid B1WC functional. The effects of the hydrostatic pressure were successfully modeled by optimizing the crystal structure and performing calculations at the elevated pressures between 0 and 20 GPa. The dependencies of the lattice constant, interionic distances, electronic and elastic properties on pressure were obtained and fitted to the linear or second order polynomial functions, which allows to get reliable estimations of all those parameters at any value of pressure in the studied range. First calculations of the Raman, IR and silent vibrational modes were performed. Not only the frequencies of the normal modes, but also the character of motion of all relevant atoms and the influence of the isotopic substitution on the vibrational frequencies were analyzed and described. Excellent agreement was found between the simulated and experimentally measured Raman spectra.

Evaluations of the Debye temperature and elastic wave velocities are discussed. The comprehensive dataset obtained in this study provides a valuable reference for the properties of the KSF crystal and can be used in modeling impurities within this material.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: M.G.B., E.A.K., A.M.S.; Methodology: L.L.R., G.Z.; Validation: L.L.R., E.A.K., M.G.B., D.B., G.Z., D.G.; Investigation: L.L.R., I.Ch.; Data Curation: L.L.R., I.Ch.; Formal Analysis: I.Ch., D.G.; Writing — Original Draft: L.L.R., E.A.K.; Writing — Review & Editing: M.G.B., D.B., D.G.; Visualization: L.L.R., D.B.; Supervision: E.A.K.; Funding Acquisition: E.A.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study was supported by Latvian Council for Science (LZP grant LZP-2023/1-0063). The research was partly performed in the Center of Excellence of the Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia, supported through European Unions Horizon 2020 Framework Programme H2020-WIDESPREAD-01-2016-2017-TeamingPhase2 under grant agreement No. 739508, project CAMART2. M.G.B. appreciates the supports from the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia under contract 451-03-47/2023-01/200017, Specialized Funding Program for the Gathering of 100 Elite Talents in Chongqing and the Overseas Talents Plan (Grant No. 2022[60]) both offered by Chongqing Association for Science and Technology and Estonian Research Council grant (PRG 2031).

Data availability Statement. The processed data are available on demand from the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: Authors thank R. Dovesi and A. Platonenko for fruitful discussions and I. Mihailovs for the technical assistance.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interests.

References

1. *Phosphor Handbook*, 3rd ed.; Liu, R.-S., Wang, X.-J., Eds.; CRC Press, Taylor and Francis Group; 2022.
2. Chen, J.; Zhao, W.; Fang, Y.; Liu, Y.; Liu, Z.; Dong, L.; Hou, J. Continuous production of $K_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$ red phosphor by green route synthesis method for warm WLEDs applications. *Opt. Mater.* **2022**, *132*, 112781.
3. Adachi, S. Review — Mn^{4+} -activated red and deep red-emitting phosphors. *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.* **2020**, *9*, 016001.
4. Sijbom, H.F.; Verstraete, R.; Joos, J.J.; Poelman, D.; Smet, P.F. $K_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$ as a red phosphor for displays and warm-white LEDs: a review of properties and perspectives. *Opt. Mater. Express* **2017**, *7*, 3332–3365.
5. Tang, F.; Su, S.; Ye, H.; Wang, M.; Lan, X.; Phillips, D.L.; Cao, Y.; Xu, S. A set of manganese ion activated fluoride phosphors ($A_2BF_6:Mn^{4+}$, A=K, Na, B=Si, Ge, Ti) synthesis below 0 C and efficient room-temperature photoluminescence. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2016**, *4*, 9561.
6. Nguyen, H.D.; Lin, C.C.; Fang, M.H.; Liu, R.S. Synthesis of $Na_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$ red phosphors for white LED applications by coprecipitation. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2014**, *2*, 10268.
7. Song, E.; Zhou, Y.; Yang, X.B.; Liao, Z.; Zhao, W.; Deng, T.; Wang, L.; Ma, Y.; Ye, S.; Zhang, Q. Highly efficient and stable narrow band red phosphor $Cs_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$ for high power warm white LED applications. *ACS Photonics* **2017**, *4*, 2556.
8. Setlur, A.A.; Radkov, E.V.; Henderson, C.S.; Her, J.-H.; Srivastava, A.M.; Karkada, N.; Satya Kishore, M.; Prasanth Kumar, N.; Aesram, D.; Deshpande, A.; Kolodin, B.; Grigorov, L.S.; Happek, U. *Chem. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 4076.
9. Radkov, E.V.; Grigorov, L.S.; Setlur, A.A.; Srivastava, A.M. U.S. Pat. #7, 497, 973 (2009).
10. Radkov, E.V.; Grigorov, L.S.; Setlur, A.A.; Srivastava, A.M. U.S. Pat.#7, 648, 649 (2010).
11. Setlur, A.A.; Siclovan, O.P.; Lyons, R.J.; Grigorov, L.S. U.S. Patent #8, 057, 706 (2011).
12. Lyons, R.J.; Setlur, A.A.; Deshpande, A.R.; Grigorov, L.S. U.S. Patent #8, 252, 613 (2012).
13. Murphy, J.E.; Setlur, A.A.; Garcia, F.; Lyons, R.J.; Chowdhury, A.I.; Karkada, N.; Kumar, N.P. U.S. Patent vol. 8, 906, 724 (2014).
14. Pust, P.; Schmidt, P.J.; Schnick, W. A revolution in lighting. *Nat. Mater.* **2015**, *14*, 454–458.
15. Brik, M.; Srivastava, A.M. Ab Initio studies of the structural, electronic, and optical properties of K_2SiF_6 singly crystals at ambient and elevated hydrostatic pressure. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2012**, *159*, J212–J216.
16. Kurboniyon, M.S.; Lou, B.; Zafari, U.; Rahimi, F.; Srivastava, A.M.; Yamamoto, T.; Brik, M.G.; Ma, C.-G. First principles study of geometric and electronic structure, and optical transition energies of Mn^{4+} impurity ions: K_2SiF_6 as a prototype. *J. Lumin.* **2023**, *263*, 120103.

- 613 17. Subhoni, M.; Zafari, U.; Ma, C.-G.; Srivastava, A.M.; Beers, W.W.; Cohen, W.E.; Brik, M.G.; Piasecki, M.; Yamamoto, T.
614 Influence of isostatic pressure on the elastic and electronic properties of $K_2SiF_6:Mn^{4+}$. *Materials* **2022**, *15*, 613.
- 615 18. The Materials Project (ID:mp-3042. DOI: 10.17188/1204828). Available online: <https://next-gen.materialsproject.org/> (ac-
616 cessed on 3 September 2024).
- 617 19. Takahashi, T.; Adachi, S. Mn^{4+} -activated red photoluminescence in K_2SiF_6 phosphor. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2008**, *155*, E183–
618 E188.
- 619 20. Saaring, J.; Vanetsev, A.; Chernenko, K.; Feldbach, E.; Kudryavtsev, I.; Mandar, H.; Pikker, S.; Parna, R.; Nagirnyi, V.;
620 Omelkov, S.; Romet, I.; Rebane, O.; Kirm, M. Time-resolved luminescence spectroscopy of ultrafast emissions in $BaGeF_6$. *J.*
621 *Lumin.* **2022**, *244*, 118729.
- 622 21. Dovesi, R.; Saunders, V.R.; Roetti, C.; Orlando, R.; Zicovich-Wilson, C.M.; Pascale, F.; Civalieri, B.; Doll, K.; Harrison, N.M.;
623 Bush, I.J.; D'Arco, P.; Llunell, M.; Causà, M.; Noël, Y.; Maschio, L.; Erba, A.; Rérat, M.; Casassa, S.; Searle, B.G.; Desmarais,
624 J.K. CRYSTAL23 User's Manual, University of Torino, Torino, 2022.
- 625 22. Dovesi, R.; Erba, A.; Orlando, R.; Zicovich-Wilson, C.M.; Civalieri, B.; Maschio, L.; Rérat, M.; Casassa, S.; Baima, J.; Salustro,
626 S.; Kirtman, B. Quantum-mechanical condensed matter simulations with CRYSTAL. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev.: Comput. Mol.*
627 *Sci.* **2018**, *8*, e1360.
- 628 23. Erba, A.; Desmarais, J.K.; Casassa, S.; Civalieri, B.; Donà, L.; Bush, I.J.; Searle, B.; Maschio, L.; Edith-Daga, L.; Cossard, A.;
629 et al. CRYSTAL23: A program for computational solid state physics and chemistry. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2023**, *19*, 6891–
630 6932.
- 631 24. Usseinov, A.B.; Gryaznov, D.; Popov, A.I.; Kotomin, E. A.; Seitov, D.; Abuova, F.; Nekrasov, K.A.; Akilbekov, A.T. *Ab initio*
632 calculations of pure and Co^{2+} -doped MgF_2 crystals. *Nucl. Inst. Meth. Phys. Res. B.* **2020**, *470*, 10.
- 633 25. Pascale, F.; Mustapha, S.; D'Arco, P.; Dovesi, R. The d orbital multi pattern occupancy in a partially filled d shell: The $KFeF_3$
634 perovskite as a test case. *Materials* **2023**, *16*, 1532.
- 635 26. Singh, V.S.; Moharil, S.V. Synthesis and characterization of K_2SiF_6 hexafluorosilicate. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **2021**,
636 *1104*, 012004.
- 637 27. Dovesi, R.; Roetti, C.; Freyria Fava, C.; Prencipe, M.; Saunders, V.R. On the elastic properties of lithium, sodium and potas-
638 sium oxide. An ab initio study. *Chem. Phys.* **1991**, *156*, 11–19.
- 639 28. CRYSTAL Basis Sets Library. Available online: https://www.crystal.unito.it/basis_sets.html (accessed on 3 September
640 2024).
- 641 29. Pascale, F.; Zicovich-Wilson, C.M.; Orlando, R.; Roetti, C.; Ugliengo, P.; Dovesi, R. Vibration frequencies of $Mg_3Al_2Si_3O_{12}$
642 pyrope. An ab initio study with the CRYSTAL code. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 6146–6152.
- 643 30. Nada, R.; Catlow, C.R.A.; Pisani, C.; Orlando, R. Ab initio Hartree-Fock perturbed-cluster study of neutral defects in LiF.
644 *Modelling. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1993**, *1*, 165–187.
- 645 31. Peintingeret, M.F.; Oliveira, D.V.; Bredow, T. Consistent Gaussian basis sets of triple-zeta valence with polarization quality
646 for solid-state calculations. *J. Comput. Chem.* **2013**, *34*, 451–459.
- 647 32. Bilc, D.I.; Orlando, R.; Shaltaf, R.; Rignanese, G.M.; Iniguez, J.; Ghosez, Ph. Hybrid exchange-correlation functional for
648 accurate prediction of the electronic and structural properties of ferroelectric oxides. *Phys. Rev. B* **2008**, *77*, 165107.
- 649 33. Wu, Z.; Cohen, R.E. More accurate generalized gradient approximation for solids. *Phys. Rev. B* **2006**, *73*, 235116.
- 650 34. Perdew, J.P.; Chevary, J.A.; Vosko, S.H.; Jackson, K.A.; Pederson, M.R.; Singh, D.J.; Fiolhais, C. Atoms, molecules, solids
651 and surfaces: Applications of the generalized gradient approximation for exchange and correlation. *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *46*,
652 6671.
- 653 35. Adamo, C.; Barone, V. Toward reliable density functional methods without adjustable parameters: The PBE0 model. *J.*
654 *Chem. Phys.* **1999**, *110*, 6158–6170.
- 655 36. Becke, A.D. Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1993**, *98*, 5648–5652.
- 656 37. Becke, A.D. Density-functional exchange-energy approximation with correct asymptotic behavior. *Phys. Rev. A* **1988**, *38*,
657 3098.
- 658 38. Lee, C.; Yang, W.; Parr, R.G. Development of the Colle-Solvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron
659 density. *Phys. Rev. B* **1988**, *37*, 785.
- 660 39. Rusevich, L.L.; Zvejnieks, G.; Kotomin, E.A. Ab initio simulation of $(Ba,Sr)TiO_3$ and $(Ba,Ca)TiO_3$ perovskite solid solutions.
661 *Solid State Ionics* **2019**, *337*, 76–81.
- 662 40. Zvejnieks, G.; Rusevich, L.L.; Gryaznov, D.; Kotomin, E.A. Interface-induced enhancement of piezoelectricity in the
663 $(SrTiO_3)_m/(BaTiO_3)_{M-m}$ superlattice for energy harvesting applications. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2019**, *21*, 23541–23551.
- 664 41. Perger, W.F.; Criswell, J.; Civalieri, B.; Dovesi, R. Ab-initio calculation of elastic constants of crystalline systems with the
665 CRYSTAL code. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **2009**, *180*, 1753–1759.
- 666 42. Erba, A.; Mahmoud, A.; Belmonte, D.; Dovesi, R. High pressure elastic properties of minerals from ab initio simulations: The
667 case of pyrope, grossular and andradite silicate garnets. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *140*, 124703.
- 668 43. Decius, J.C.; Hexter, R.M. *Molecular Vibrations in Crystals*; McGraw-Hill, New York, 1977.
- 669 44. Dovesi, R.; De La Pierre, M.; Ferrari, A.M.; Pascale, F.; Maschio, L.; Zicovich-Wilson, C.M. The IR vibrational properties of
670 six members of the garnet family: A quantum mechanical ab initio study. *Am. Miner.* **2011**, *96*, 1787–1798.
- 671 45. Hurst, G.J.B.; Dupuis, M.; Clementi, E. Ab initio analytic polarizability, first and second hyperpolarizabilities of large con-
672 jugated organic molecules: applications to polyenes C_4H_6 to $C_{22}H_{24}$. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1988**, *89*, 385–395.

- 673 46. Kirtman, B.; Gu, F.L.; Bishop, D.M. Extension of the Genkin and Mednis treatment for dynamic polarizabilities and hy-
674 perpolarizabilities of infinite periodic systems. I. Coupled perturbed Hartree-Fock theory. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2000**, *113*, 1294–
675 1309.
- 676 47. Dovesi, R.; Kirtman, B.; Maschio, L.; Maul, J.; Pascale, F.; Rérat, M. Calculation of the infrared intensity of crystalline sys-
677 tems. A comparison of three strategies based on Berry phase, Wannier function, and coupled-perturbed Kohn–Sham meth-
678 ods. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2019**, *123*, 8336–8346.
- 679 48. Rusevich, L.L.; Kotomin, E.A.; Zvejnieks, G.; Popov, A.I. Ab initio calculations of structural, electronic and vibrational
680 properties of BaTiO₃ and SrTiO₃ perovskite crystals with oxygen vacancies. *Low Temp. Phys.* **2020**, *46*, 1185–1195.
- 681 49. Rusevich, L.L.; Kotomin, E.A.; Popov, A.I.; Aiello, G.; Scherer, T.A.; Lushchik, A. The vibrational and dielectric properties
682 of diamond with N impurities: First principles study. *Diamond Relat. Mater.* **2022**, *130*, 109399.
- 683 50. Rusevich, L.L.; Kotomin, E.A.; Popov, A.I.; Aiello, G.; Scherer, T.A.; Lushchik, A. The electronic, vibrational and dielectric
684 properties of diamond crystals with neutral vacancies: first principles study. *Opt. Mater.* **2024**, *150*, 115222.
- 685 51. Maschio, L.; Kirtman, B.; Rérat, M.; Orlando, R.; Dovesi, R. Ab initio analytical Raman intensities for periodic systems
686 through a coupled perturbed Hartree-Fock/Kohn-Sham method in an atomic orbital basis. I. Theory. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**,
687 *139*, 164101.
- 688 52. Maschio, L.; Kirtman, B.; Rérat, M.; Orlando, R.; Dovesi, R. Ab initio analytical Raman intensities for periodic systems
689 through a coupled perturbed Hartree-Fock/Kohn-Sham method in an atomic orbital basis. II. Validation and comparison
690 with experiments. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *139*, 164102.
- 691 53. Lazarowska, A.; Mahlik, S.; Grinberg, M.; Lin, C.C.; Liu, R.-S. Pressure effect on the zero-phonon line emission of Mn⁴⁺ in
692 K₂SiF₆. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *143*, 134704.
- 693 54. Schreiber, E.; Anderson, O.L.; Soga, N. *Elastic constants and their measurements*; McGraw-Hill, New York, 1973.
- 694 55. Poirier, J.; Brown, J.M. Introduction to the physics of the Earth's deep interior. *Phys. Today* **1992**, *45*, 66–67.
- 695 56. Anderson, O.L. A simplified method for calculating the Debye temperature from elastic constants. *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*
696 **1963**, *24*, 909–917.
- 697

698 **Disclaimer/Publisher's Note:** The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual au-
699 thor(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to
700 people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.